

Radical Mediated Reactions in Organic Synthesis

N. S. NARASIMHAN*, INDRAPAL SINGH AIDHEN and N. M. SUNDER

Garware Research Centre, Department of Chemistry, University of Poona, Pune-411 007

RADICAL reactions have several distinguishing features. For this reason, they are now being increasingly used in organic synthesis, particularly for the construction of carbon-carbon bonds.

Carbon radicals can be formed by cleavage of bonds, which are generally not favoured in ionic reactions¹ (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Carbon radicals show considerable chemoselectivity. Thus they attack C=C and not C=O. Other functional groups such as OH, CN and COOR are also not attacked. A typical example² is shown in Scheme 2.

Scheme 2

Carbon radicals show regioselectivity. Their reaction with C=C is complementary to reactions of carbenium ions³ (Scheme 3).

Scheme 3

Although stereochemistry of carbon radical reactions are poor, in specific cases these are reasonable for synthetic exploitation. Thus the carbon radical from a sugar reacts to give mainly the equatorial isomer⁴ (Scheme 4).

Scheme 4

Radical reactions are fast. Therefore, side reactions, such as rearrangement, elimination and racemisation are generally not encountered in their reactions. In the following example⁵ (Scheme 5), thus, no racemisation is observed⁵.

Scheme 5

Finally, radical reactions have complementary reactivity to ionic reactions. They exhibit umpolung of reactivity vis-a-vis ionic reactions⁶ (Scheme 6).

Scheme 6

Carbon radicals can be generated thermally, photochemically and electrochemically. Metal stabilised radicals are also available. Some of the methods for generation of carbon radicals are under mild and neutral conditions. In these cases, especially, the radical reactions exhibit, generally, no side reactions, such as elimination, rearrangement and racemisation. Some of the methods for generation of carbon radicals are given below¹.

C-H bond cleavage :

C-O bond cleavage :

C-X bond cleavage (X = halogen, SePh, BR₂, etc.) :

C-C bond cleavage :

Generation of aryl radicals :

Fredericamycin-A—A new synthesis of the spiro structure :

Fredericamycin-A (1), a powerful antitumour agent, has the novel spirodiketone unit⁷. Several methods are available for building of this unit.

Of particular interest are the methods using the indanedione precursors 2, which are cyclised to the spirostructure. Two approaches are known here. In one, the carbanion, from the indanedione moiety is cyclised at the aromatic position carrying a halogen atom in presence of Pd(O) (Scheme 7)⁸.

Scheme 7

In the other, the carbanion is coupled to the aromatic ring, which bears a suitably placed

hydroxyl group, by oxidising agents such as alkaline ferricyanide (Scheme 8)*.

Scheme 8

As shown above, in the first, a halogen is necessary at the position of cyclisation, and in the second, a hydroxyl group, which then brings about the cyclisation preponderantly at the *para* position rather than the *ortho*.

We considered the possibility of cyclisation of the indanedione precursor 3, which did not have a halogen or an hydroxyl substituent in the second ring (Scheme 9), through a radical generated at the *active* methine position.

Scheme 9

Radical 4 was sought to be generated by oxidation with manganese(III) acetate. Generation of α -carbon radicals, from enolisable carbonyl compounds, on oxidation with manganese(III) acetate is well-known¹.

The starting compound 3 for the above reaction was made according to the sequence shown in Scheme 10.

Scheme 10

The oxidation was carried out in acetic acid solution with 2 equivalents of manganese(III) acetate. A compound was obtained in 30–35% yield, which was characterised as the dimer 6. Obviously, the desired radical had formed, but did not cyclise intramolecularly onto the other aromatic ring but underwent an intermolecular coupling reaction. To promote the intramolecular cyclisation, the reaction was carried out in dilute solution. However, once again only the dimer was formed.

The radical formed in the above reaction is α to the carbonyl group. It is therefore electrophilic. It was then hoped that the cyclisation reaction would be favoured if the second benzene ring carried a methoxyl group at the *ortho* or *para* position with respect to the position of cyclisation. The manganese(III) acetate oxidation was then carried out with the substrate 7. The reaction now gave both the cyclised compound 8 (yield 25–30%) and the dimer 9 (35%), the latter in major amount (Scheme 11).

Scheme 11

The spiro compound 8 was obtained as a major compound in 30–40% when the reaction was carried out in dilute solution. Interestingly, in this reaction, only the *ortho*-cyclised compound 8 was obtained. This is in contrast to the oxidative coupling of phenolic compounds with alkaline ferricyanide. The *ortho* compound is presumably formed due to the methoxyl oxygen and carbonyl oxygen chelating with Mn^{III} , which then promotes the observed regioselectivity (Scheme 12).

Scheme 12

Steganone – A new intramolecular arylation reaction: Steganone (11) is a lignan lactone with remarkable antitumour activity¹⁰. Its synthesis has been achieved by several workers, one of which being from 9-phenanthrylamine (10) by the sequence shown in Scheme 13¹¹.

Scheme 13

We projected a synthesis of the phenanthrylamine (10) according to Scheme 14, the novelty of which was an intramolecular arylation, in which the aryl radical was generated from an arylhalide.

Scheme 14

Radical mediated intramolecular arylation are indeed well-known. The synthetically most exploited are the Pschorr ring closure of the aryl-diazonium compounds and the alkaline ferricyanide oxidative-coupling of phenols.

Recently, arylradicals have been conveniently generated from arylbromides and iodides with Bu_3SnH and initiator AIBN¹. These aryl radicals have been reacted intramolecularly with carbon-carbon double bonds to give condensed ring compounds (Scheme 15)^{1a}.

Scheme 15

Arylation of benzene rings by the Bu_3SnH methodology, however, is not reported. The proposed synthesis of steganone (Scheme 14) was the first attempt on these lines.

The starting compound 12 for the cyclisation reaction was prepared according to Scheme 16.

Scheme 16

When the bromo compound was refluxed in benzene solution with $Bu_3SnH/AIBN$, a phenanthrol

was obtained in 23% yield. It was, however, not the required compound 14, but the isomer 15 (Scheme 17).

Scheme 17

The structure of the compound 15 was established by spectral analysis, but more firmly by an alternate synthesis by a standard method (Scheme 18)^{1a}.

Scheme 18

A possible mechanism for the formation of the isomeric compound 15, could be as shown in Scheme 19.

Scheme 19

In the mechanism an *ipso* attack occurs, which is presumably favoured because the aryl radical is a σ -radical and the *ipso* attack will also be geometrically favoured. The intermediate then rearranges to the completely aromatised system. Here two possibilities exist, one by migration of the aryl group to give **14** and the other by migration of the methylene group to give **15**. In the above reaction, the latter is favoured. It may be noted that, of the two migrating bonds in the spiro intermediate **17**, one is between sp^3C and sp^2C , and the other is between two sp^2C atoms. There exists thus a differentiation between the two bonds and only the bond between two sp^2C atoms migrates. It was thought that in the spiro intermediate **19**, where both the spirobonds are between the sp^2C atoms, a possibility of either of the bond migrating would exist (Scheme 20).

Scheme 20

When compound **18**, prepared from **12**, was refluxed in benzene solution with $Bu_3SnH/AIBN$, compound **21** was obtained (yield 66%). But, more gratifyingly it was the only product. Thus compound **21** was synthesised, which constitutes a formal synthesis of steganone itself.

Camptothecin – A new synthesis of 2,3-dihydropyrrolo[3,4-*b*]quinoline : 2,3-Dihydropyrrolo[3,4-*b*]quinoline (**22**) is the starting compound for several of the syntheses of camptothecin (**23**), the antileukemic alkaloid¹⁴.

Our objective was to obtain **22** by the lithiation of 3-hydroxymethylquinoline according to Scheme 21, which was in analogy with lithiation of benzyl alcohols¹⁵.

Scheme 21

The lithiation reaction, however, proceeded to yield 2-butyl-3-hydroxymethylquinoline (**28**) at room temperature and also at -78° .

Metal-halogen exchange is another method to introduce a lithium atom at an aromatic position¹⁶. The 2-iodo-3-hydroxymethylquinoline (**24**) was then synthesised and its lithiation studied. The compound was treated with *n*-BuLi at -78° and the metalation mixture further reacted with DMF (Scheme 22). This reaction gave neither the required 2-formyl compound (**26**), nor the 2-butyl compound (**28**), nor even the starting compound **24**, but only the reduced 2-H compound **29**.

Scheme 22

The formation of the 2-H compound (**29**) indicated that the 2-lithio compound was indeed formed in this reaction. However, it had not reacted with DMF, but only with an acidic hydrogen during the reaction (!) or during work-up. In order to check whether the 2-lithio compound had reacted with an acidic hydrogen of water during aqueous work-up, in one reaction, the compound **24**, after lithiation, was treated with D_2O , and further subjected to aqueous work-up⁷ (Scheme 23).

Scheme 23

Interestingly, the reaction gave the 2-D compound **30** only in 27% yield. The 2-H compound **29** was formed in 63% yield.

In seeking an explanation for the above result, a mechanism was considered in which the *n*-BuLi reacted first with the C-I bond rather than with the acidic hydrogen of compound **24**. Several reports^{1†} are available in which it is proposed that *n*-BuLi reacts faster with a carbon-halogen bond than with an acidic hydrogen. Some of these are indicated in Scheme 24[†].

Scheme 24

In the present case a mechanism (Scheme 25) was considered for the formation of the 2-H product **29**.

Scheme 25

The above mechanism was further supported when the O-deuterated compound **34**, in a similar reaction (Scheme 26), gave the 2-D compound **30** in 60% yield, even when worked-up with only H₂O. In this reaction, **29** was also formed to the extent of 30%.

Scheme 26

That *n*-BuLi should react faster with a C-I bond rather than with an acidic hydrogen is surprising. An explanation, however, is possible if

the reaction of *n*-BuLi with a C-I bond is a single-electron transfer radical reaction and that with an acidic hydrogen a paired-electron transfer ionic acid-base reaction. Metal-halogen exchange, indeed, is considered to be a radical reaction by several workers^{1,8}.

The reaction of *n*-BuLi with a carbonyl group is most likely a paired-electron transfer nucleophilic ionic reaction. If this is so, the reaction of *n*-BuLi with a C-I bond would also be faster than that with a C=O. To test this, the formyl derivative **35** was prepared and lithiated with the expectation that the 2-lithio compound **36** initially formed would further react, intramolecularly, with the formyl group to give the 2-formyl compound **38** (Scheme 27).

Scheme 27

This was indeed realised. Compound **38** was obtained in 56% yield in the above reaction. Compound **38** has been converted to **22** by reduction to the diol **39** followed by treatment with ammonia^{1,9}.

Summary: The paper describes some radical mediated reactions. Two of them, i.e. generation of aryl radicals by heating an arylhalide in benzene solution with Bu₃SnH and a radical initiator (AIBN), and the generation of α-keto carbon radicals by heating a 1,3-diketone in acetic acid solution with manganese(III) acetate, are conventional ones. The third one, i.e. radical mediated metal-exchange reaction¹⁰, although synthetically much exploited, is mechanistically less firmly established. Lastly, examples are also given where a metal-halogen exchange reaction occurs faster than the reaction of the alkyl-lithium reagent with an acidic hydrogen or with a carbonyl group.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (N.S.N.) thanks Department of Science and Technology, New Delhi, for funds to implement some part of the research work. Two of the authors (I.P.S. and N.M.S.) thank C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for Junior Research Fellowships.

References

1. B. GIBSE, "Radicals in Organic Synthesis: Formation of Carbon-Carbon Bonds", Pergamon, New York, 1986.
2. G. STORK and N. H. BAINE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1982, 104, 2321.

3. A. L. J. BECKWITH and K. U. INGOLD in "Rearrangement in Ground and Excited States", ed. P. DE MAYO, Academic, New York, 1980, Vol. 1, p. 161, A. L. J. BECKWITH and C. H. SCHIESSER, *Tetrahedron*, 1986, 41, 9925.
4. B. GIESE and K. GRONINGER, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1984, 25, 2743.
5. R. M. ADLINGTON, J. E. BALDWIN, A. BASAK and R. P. KOZYROD, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1983, 944.
6. B. GIESE and J. BUPUIS, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1983, 22, 622, R. R. SCHMIDT and M. HOFFMANN, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1983, 22, 406.
7. R. C. PANDE, *J. Antibiotics*, 1981, 34, 1389, R. S. MISRA, R. C. PANDE and J. V. SILVERTON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1982, 104, 4478.
8. M. A. CIUFOLINI and M. E. BROWNE, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1988, 53, 4150; *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1987, 28, 171.
9. A. S. KRNDI, F. H. EBETINO and T. OHTA, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1985, 26, 3063.
10. S. M. KUPCHAN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1973, 95, 1385.
11. D. BECKER, L. R. HUGHES and R. A. RAPHAEL, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans 1*, 1977, 1674.
12. V. SNIECKUS, C. P. SLOAN and K. SHANKARAN, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1985, 49, 6001.
13. F. B. MALLORY and C. W. MALLORY, *Org. React.*, 1984, 30, 1.
14. J. C. CAI and O. R. HURCHINSON in "The Alkaloids - Chemistry and Pharmacology", ed. A. BRASSI, Academic, New York, 1983, Vol. 21, p. 101.
15. D. SEEBACH and N. MEYER, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1978, 17, 521, *Chem. Ber.*, 1980, 113, 1804.
16. O. METH-COHN *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans 1*, 1981, 2509.
17. C. A. STEIN and T. A. MORTON, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1973, 4933, R. J. BOATMAN *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1977, 99, 4822.
18. P. J. BARKER and J. N. WINTER in "The Chemistry of the Metal-Carbon Bond", eds F. R. HARTLEY and S. PATAI, Wiley, New York, 1985, Vol. 2, p. 164.
19. E. J. COREY, D. N. CROUSE and J. E. ANDERSON, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1975, 40, 2140.
20. Here discrete radicals are perhaps not formed and the exchange reaction takes place in the solvent cage.